

External Interventions and the Rehabilitations of Internally Displaced Persons in Adamawa State: the role of International Non-Governmental Organizations

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This study evaluates the role of International NON-Governmental Organization on humanitarian assistance for Internally Displaced Persons in Adamawa State. It adopted primary and secondary method; the primary method used the instrument of questionnaire and interview. While secondary method relied on documented materials such as Text books on International Non-Governmental Organization, Journals, conference materials/articles, annual publication on the activities of International Non-Governmental Organization. Other materials were sourced from Internet (International Non-Governmental Organization website). Regression analysis was used to analyze the collected data. The study adopted Neo-liberal theory. The findings from the study reveal that, International Non-governmental Organization (INGOs) has played a significant role in the rehabilitations of internally

displaced persons in Adamawa State. Some of the activities of INGO to Internally Displaced Persons include; emergency food aids, materials relief assistance and services, relief coordination, protection and support services, basic nutrition, disaster prevention preparedness, reconstruction relief and rehabilitation, basic health care, ending violence against women and girls, agricultural development, basic drinking water, and basic sanitation and other sectors. The study recommended that, International Non-Governmental Organization should continue with the role of humanitarian assistance for sustainable livelihood of the Internally Displaced Persons in Adamawa state.

Keywords: Rehabilitations, Internally Displaced Persons, International NON-Governmental Organization, humanitarian assistance

INTRODUCTION

Addressing the humanitarian crisis and breaking the cycle of hunger among the internally displaced populations, requires investment in the right kind of programmes. This is why the International Non-Governmental Organizations (INGOs) has been working with the government to design programmes that address short term needs and at the same time build the resilience of households and communities. In the last 10 year, International NGOs have strengthened their links with other actors, including in the health, agricultural and educational sector to assist the displaced persons in Adamawa State (Amnesty International, 2016). These approaches to development of internally displaced

populations increasingly have an eye for human capital, promotion and protection of human right, hygiene, food security etc. The strategies to achieved this include; daily feeding programmes in schools aim to prevent children from dropping out, food assistance to communities are being organized to address the causes of food insecurity, building roads that connect communities to markets, health facilities and schools. This article seeks to evaluate the role of International Non-governmental Organizations in addressing the socio-economic challenges of the internally displaced persons (Amnesty International, 2016:6).

Globalization has given opportunities to International

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to emerge on the world stage as one of the central players in the processes of development around the world (Fisher, 2013). The emergence of new actors in the humanitarians' field raises questions not only about their impact on citizens, but also their impact on socio-economic development of the internally displaced persons in Adamawa State. The existing gap between Government effort in providing social amenities and the need to economically empower the internally displaced persons have provided the need for the International Non-Governmental Organizations (INGOs) to operate (Willets, 2010). Insecurity has strengthened the role of INGOs in empowering the internally displaced persons in Adamawa State; they are one of the most influential players in social welfare of internally displaced persons. Despite the intervention of INGOs, there are still cases of Humanitarians crisis in Adamawa State. Questions still linger, as to whether there is need to further explore the role of International INGOs on rehabilitations of internally displaced persons in Adamawa State. INGOs are international donor community aimed at bringing fresh solutions to longstanding development problems characterized by inefficient government to government aid and ineffective development projects. Within the subsequent effort to liberalize economies and "roll back" the state as part of structural adjustment policies, NGOs came also to be seen as a cost-effective alternative to public sector service delivery (David, 2017). International Non-governmental organizations (INGOs) are now recognized as key third sector actors on the landscapes of development, human rights, humanitarian action, environment, and many other areas of public action, from the post-2004 tsunami reconstruction efforts in Indonesia, India, Thailand, and Sri Lanka, to the 2005 Make Poverty History campaign for aid and trade reform and developing country debt cancellation (David, 2017:19). INGOs are best known for interrelated, types of activity, the delivery of services to people in need, and the organization of policy advocacy, and public campaigns in pursuit of social transformation. INGOs are also active in a wide range of other specialized roles such as democracy building, conflict resolution, human rights work, cultural preservation, environmental activism, policy analysis, research, and information provision. This chapter mainly confines itself to a discussion of INGOs in the international development context, but much of its argument also applies to INGOs more widely (David, 2017:21). Lewis, (2017) defined INGOs from the three main components: implementer, catalyst, and partner (Lewis, 2017). The implementer role is concerned with the mobilization of resources to provide goods and services to people who need them. Service delivery is carried out by NGOs across a wide range of fields such as healthcare, microfinance, agricultural extension, emergency relief, and human rights. This role has increased as INGOs have been increasingly 'contracted'

by governments and donors with governance reform and privatization policies to carry out specific tasks in return for payment; it has also become more prominent as INGOs are increasingly responding to man-made emergencies or natural disasters with humanitarian assistance. The catalyst role can be defined as an INGO's ability to inspire, facilitate or contribute to improved thinking and action to promote social transformation. This effort may be directed towards individuals or groups in local communities, or among other actors in development such as government, business or donors. It may include grassroots organizing and group formation, gender and empowerment work, lobbying and advocacy work, and attempts to influence wider policy processes through innovation, and policy entrepreneurship. The role of partner reflects the growing trend for INGOs to work with government, donors and the private sector on joint activities, such as providing specific inputs within a broader multiagency program or project, or undertaking socially responsible business initiatives (Daniela, 2010). It also includes activities that take place among INGOs and with communities such as "capacity building" work which seeks to develop and strengthen capabilities. The current policy rhetoric of "partnership" seeks to bring INGOs into mutually beneficial relationships with these other sectors. Morris-Suzuki, (2010) defined INGOs as a charitable and paternalistic organization that seek to pursue radical or "empowerment" based approaches. Morris-Suzuki, (2010) further said that, INGOs aim to meet only people's immediate needs, while others take a longer-term view and seek to develop alternative ideas and approaches to problems. A single INGO might combine several of these different elements at any one time. Morris-Suzuki (2010: 68) notes that "INGOs may pursue change, but they can equally work to maintain existing social and political systems." Radicals INGOs seek to explore alternative visions of development and change or seen as progressive vehicles for change. INGOs may be regarded as part of market-based solutions to policy problems (Morris-Suzuki, 2010: 68). A key point to note here is that INGOs can be seen as a kind of tabula rasa, onto which a range of current ideas, expectations, and anxieties about social transformation are projected (Lewis, 2015a). It is partly because of this high degree of flexibility of the INGO as an institutional form, and the wide spectrum of different values that INGOs may contain, that the rise to prominence of INGOs since the late 1980s has taken place against the back-drop of the ascendancy of neoliberal policy agendas (Lewis, 2015b:74).

Bebbington et al. (2008) defined INGOs in term of relationship to social transformation. For some, INGOs are useful actors because they can provide cost-effective services in flexible ways, while for others they are campaigners fighting for change or generating new ideas and approaches to development problems. The fact that INGOs have now become the focus of criticism from

many different political perspectives is both a reflection of the wide diversity of INGO types and roles that exist, and of their increasing power and importance in the twenty-first century. The large volume of resources that they receive combined with the fact that INGOs receive a higher level of public exposure and scrutiny than ever before, speaks to their continuing importance. Perhaps there is now a more realistic view among policy makers about what NGOs can and cannot achieve (Bebbington et al., 2008:62).

Today INGOs deliver more official development assistance than the entire U.N. system (excluding the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund) (Mathews, 2017). Social scientists have begun to take new interest in the increasing role of INGOs in environmental protection, gender justice, human rights etc. Kaldor, (2013) argues that global civil society in the 1990s was dominated by NGOs changing the norms concerning human rights and humanitarian intervention. NGOs wielding tremendous power are also important from post-conflict reconstruction perspectives (Kaldor, 2013). Claude (2011), state the role of NGOs increased and become political as NGOs gained legitimacy, shaped international public opinion, and formed coalitions with sympathetic governments”.

The concept of International Non-Governmental Organization in the context of this study means a voluntary, independent networking body that supports and effectively responds to the humanitarian and development needs in Adamawa (Agg, 2016). The organisations provide assistance to the internally displaced persons regardless of ethnic background, affiliation, or religious belief. Neo-Liberal theory approach explained the role of state and non-state actor in their commitment to social welfare, human, social rights and social work's role in promoting, protecting and enforcement of development programme of the society (Molyneux, 2008). This informs the important of this theory to the study. In this paper therefore, the study seeks to analyze the role played by International NGOs in the rehabilitations of internally displaced persons in Adamawa State.

METHODOLOGY

Survey and documentary data research design method was chosen by the researcher; because it enables the research to gather information from both primary and secondary sources. The population for this study covers staff of the selected International Non-governmental Organization. The organizations are; Amnesty international, Oxfam international, Red Cross and Care International, selected victims of human right violation, Internally Displaced Persons in Adamawa State, selected military personnel and journalists. Stratified and Purposive sampling technique was used to determine the

sample size from the entire population. The study adopted both primary and secondary method. The primary data were generated with the instrument of questionnaire and interview. The questionnaires were distributed to the staff of International Committee of the Red Cross and Oxfam International in Maitama-Abuja. Interviews were conducted on some selected Internally Displaced Persons Camp in Mubi-Adamawa State. Staff at IDPS camp was interviewed in order to compliment the response from the Staff of the INGOs. Few military personnel and Journalists were also interviewed. The study relied on Secondary data collected from; Text books on International Non-Governmental Organization, Journals and conference materials/articles on the activities of International Non-Governmental Organization, International Non-Governmental Organization annual publication on Humanitarian responses as well as statistics material on the beneficiary of Humanitarian responses. Other materials were sourced from Internet (International Non-Governmental Organization website (www.amnestyinternational.org)). Primary data generated was analyzed with the used of the quantitative statistical tool. The data collected was presented in tables, using absolute figures and the corresponding percentages capable of self explanation and further analysis. Hypotheses testing were done with the use of chi-square method of data analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 5% (percent) level of significance. At 5% level of significance, null hypothesis was rejected for test with probability estimate lower than 5% (0.05) and conclude that they are statistically significant by accepting alternative hypothesis with probability estimates are above 5%.

RESULTS

Data obtained revealed that, 27 respondents representing 55.1% agreed were of the view that OXFAM International has taken all appropriate measures to suppress all forms of traffic in women and exploitation of prostitution of women. 18 respondents representing 36.7% disagreed while, 4 respondents representing 8.2% could not ascertain whether OXFAM International has take all appropriate measures to suppress all forms of traffic in women and exploitation of prostitution of women (Table 1). Data obtained revealed that, 26 respondents representing 53.1% agreed were of the view that OXFAM International has improved the enrolment of children in schools. 19 respondents representing 38.8% disagreed while, 4 respondents representing 8.2% could not ascertain whether OXFAM International has improved the enrolment of children in schools (Table 2).

Data obtained revealed that, 27 respondents representing 55.1% agreed were of the view that OXFAM International has taken all appropriate measures to suppress all forms of traffic in women and exploitation of

Table 1. OXFAM International has taken all appropriate measures to suppress all forms of traffic in women and exploitation of prostitution of women.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	27	31.4	55.1	55.1
	Disagree	18	20.9	36.7	91.8
	Undecided	4	4.7	8.2	100.0
	Total	49	57.0	100.0	
Missing system		37	43.0		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 2. OXFAM International has improved the enrolment of children in schools.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	26	30.2	53.1	53.1
	Disagree	19	22.1	38.8	91.8
	Undecided	4	4.7	8.2	100.0
	Total	49	57.0	100.0	
Missing System		37	43.0		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Table 3. OXFAM International has provided development and advancement of women.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	27	31.4	55.1	55.1
	Disagree	18	20.9	36.7	91.8
	Undecided	4	4.7	8.2	100.0
	Total	49	57.0	100.0	
Missing system		37	43.0		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Table 4. Red Cross has supported the development of alternative income generating activities for farmers and women.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	25	29.1	43.9	43.9
	Disagree	20	23.3	35.1	78.9
	Undecided	12	14.0	21.1	100.0
	Total	57	66.3	100.0	
Missing system		29	33.7		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

prostitution of women. 18 respondents representing 36.7% disagreed while, 4 respondents representing 8.2% could not ascertain whether OXFAM International has taken all appropriate measures to suppress all forms of traffic in women and exploitation of prostitution of women (Table 3). Data obtained revealed that, 25 respondents representing 43.9% agreed were of the view that Red Cross has supported the development of alternative income generating activities for farmers and women. 20 respondents representing 35.1% disagreed while, 14

respondents representing 21.1% could not ascertain whether Red Cross has supported the development of alternative income generating activities for farmers and women (Table 4). Data obtained revealed that, 38 respondents representing 66.7% agreed were of the view that Red Cross has supported primary health care clinics and community health service. 10 respondents representing 17.5% disagreed while, 9 respondents representing 15.8% could not ascertain whether Red Cross has supported primary health care clinics and

Table 5. Red Cross has supported primary health care clinics and community health service.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	38	44.2	66.7	66.7
	Disagree	10	11.6	17.5	84.2
	Undecided	9	10.5	15.8	100.0
	Total	57	66.3	100.0	
Missing system		29	33.7		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Table 6. Red Cross has distributed relief materials and household foods to victims of Human right abuses.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	27	31.4	47.4	47.4
	Disagree	20	23.3	35.1	82.5
	Undecided	10	11.6	17.5	100.0
	Total	57	66.3	100.0	
Missing System		29	33.7		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Table 7. Red Cross has improved living conditions of detainees in Prisons.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	24	27.9	42.1	42.1
	Disagree	19	22.1	33.3	75.4
	Undecided	14	16.3	24.6	100.0
	Total	57	66.3	100.0	
Missing System		29	33.7		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

community health service (Table 5). Data obtained revealed that, 27 respondents representing 47.4% agreed were of the view that Red Cross has distributed relief materials and household foods to victims of Human right abuses. 20 respondents representing 35.1% disagreed while, 10 respondents representing 17.5% could not ascertain whether Red Cross has distributed relief materials and household foods to victims of Human right abuses (Table 6). Data obtained revealed that, 24 respondents representing 42.1% agreed were of the view that Red Cross has supported the development of alternative income generating activities for farmers and women. 19 respondents representing 33.3% disagreed while, 14 respondents representing 24.6% could not ascertain whether Red Cross has supported the development of alternative income generating activities for farmers and women (Table 7). Data obtained revealed that, 31 respondents representing 57.4% agreed were of the view that INGOs has safeguarded the right of Adamawa State citizens. 18 respondents representing 33.3% disagreed while, 5 respondents representing 9% could not ascertain whether INGOs has safeguarded the right of Adamawa State citizens (Table 8).

Table 9 shows the calculated value of chi-square $X^2=37.23$ while the critical value of chi-square $X = 9.49$ at 4 degree of freedom under 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated value of X^2 (37.23) is greater than the critical value of X (9.49) and the P-Value of 0.000 is less than the alpha value of 0.005, we can reject the null hypothesis that stated that, There is no significance relationship between the role of OXFAM International in improving the enrolment of children in schools and Human right protection in Adamawa State and accept the alternative hypothesis. This means that, there is a significance relationship between the role of OXFAM International in improving the enrolment of children in schools and Human right protection in Adamawa State.

The projects of the Oxfam international included the construction of 79 boreholes, 20 water purification units and 137 latrines, benefiting about 490,000 people. In addition, way stations benefitted 7,580 returnees, 8,000 mosquito nets were distributed and 2,800 households received agricultural tools, seeds, and fishing nets for their livelihood. Besides these outcomes, such projects as hygiene workshops at schools and communities and training in water management, agriculture and fishery

Table 8. INGOs has safeguarded the right of Adamawa State citizens.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	31	25.6	57.4	40.7
	Disagree	18	26.7	33.3	83.3
	Undecided	5	10.5	9.3	100.0
	Total	54	62.8	100.0	
Missing System		32	37.2		
Total		86	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Table 9. Chi-Square tests.

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	37.230 ^a	4	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	33.411	4	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	44.144	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	36.471	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	49				

Table 10. Chi-Square tests.

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	73.112 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	69.363	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	42.475	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	54		

were also implemented in the Adamawa States (Interviewed official of Refugees commission on 27th November, 2019). This finding was in line with the Interview conducted; Oxfam international embarked on projects regarding basic health for pregnant and lactating women and children in Adamawa State. ADRA shifted its focus from assistance for returnees to awareness rising of HIV/AIDS and livelihood assistance. Oxfam international expanded the scope of its projects by including projects on education and assistance for socially vulnerable groups.

Ho: There is no significance relationship between the role of Red Cross in distributing relief materials and household foods to victims of Human right abuses in Adamawa State.

Table 10 shows the calculated value of chi-square $X^2=73.11$ while the critical value of chi-square $X = 9.49$ at 4 degree of freedom under 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated value of X^2 (73.11) is greater than the critical value of X (9.49) and the P-Value of 0.000 is less than the alpha value of 0.005, we can reject the null hypothesis that stated that, There is no significance relationship between the role of Red Cross in distributing relief materials and household foods to victims of Human right abuses in Adamawa State and accept the alternative

hypothesis. This means that, there is a significance relationship between the role of Red Cross in distributing relief materials and household foods to victims of Human right abuses in Adamawa State. The military personnel interviewed reveals that, there were armed clashes and attacks on women, children, humanitarian workers and other security incidents continue to result in civilian deaths, displacement and disease outbreak. This finding was in line with the Interview conducted; Red Cross has intervention Programme that focus on improving access and quality of health services with attention to mothers and children, infrastructure development, health system strengthening, human resource development and capacity development with a passion of improving the health outcomes in the communities that we serve.

DISCUSSION

Findings from the study revealed that, there is a significance relationship between the role of OXFAM International in improving the enrolment of children in schools and Human right protection in Adamawa State. This finding is in line with the Oxfam international report (2015) it indicate that, many have returned home to help build the new nation. After decades of war, Adamawa State needs to be built almost from scratch, and there are

enormous challenges. Most people still do not have access to clean water, sanitation, or adequate schools or healthcare. Oxfam international has assisted in the returned of over 180,000 southerners returned from the north of Sudan, provided access to clean water, improved sanitation, or build and rehabilitated schools to increase children enrolment and improved the condition of healthcare facilities.

Findings from the study reveals that, there is significance relationship between the role of Red Cross in distributing relief materials and household foods to victims of Human right abuses and Human right protection in Adamawa State.

This finding is in line with the view of the Percival, (2018:1). ICRC supports communities with food, water, sanitation, building programmes and medical aid. They help people to grow their own food and run immunisation programmes for cattle, as cows are the main source of wealth and prestige in South Sudan.

Interview with the internally displaced persons in mubi, yola, Minchika reveals that, community hospital in most place is resourced by International assistance and includes a fully equipped medical team, supplying all the medicines and supporting local health workers as government health system are not reliable. Her main focus was treating weapon wounds, mainly from gunshots. They also treated children and locals suffering common medical conditions: severe malnutrition, pneumonia (in small children), gastro bugs, and hepatitis. The Red Cross has dispatched non-food items for Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs), the items being transported include mosquito nets, blankets, tarpaulins and hygiene kits. Provision of International Red cross helps to gain and maintain humanitarian access in areas of displacement, and provides tangible and visible support to IDPs, host communities, national and local authorities, even where there is no government presence. The role of OXFAM International on human right protection include; improving the enrolment of children in schools among the Adamawa State. It has assisted in the returned of over 180,000 people to their home, provided access to clean water, improved sanitation, or build and rehabilitated schools to increase children enrolment and improved the condition of healthcare facilities.

The role of Red Cross on humanitarians assistance include; supports communities with food, water, sanitation, building programmes and medical aid. They help people to grow their own food and run immunisation programmes for cattle, as cows are the main source of wealth and prestige in Adamawa State. Red Cross assistance programme in Adamawa has transformed lives of approximately 637,851 people by delivering development, humanitarian and emergency interventions to 456,133 People, including mothers and children, received disease prevention and treatment, 86,105 People were reached with peace messages and participated in outreaches for nation building. 5,000

farmers in Michika were trained in dry season vegetable production for market and household use. 54,301 Vulnerable population in Juba town empowered through work for cash-for assets projects to uplift their status 36,312 Refugees and internally displaced people affected by conflict received support to help them regain their means of livelihoods in the areas of health care services in maternal and child health, nutrition, HIV/AIDS testing and counselling, and immunization in Communities (Interviewed IDPs Camp official on 27th January, 2019). The intervention programme have Strengthened health systems. It has supported the recruitment, training and retention of health workers; developed capacity of health workers through training, support supervision and mentorship; strengthened community structures for an efficient health referral system and jointly developed the community Health Strategic plan for communities (2018-2025). There is increasing human resource in health, it has help in running the Mubi Nursing Training School, graduating nurses and midwives to service in the State Ministry of Health.

Red Cross have been actively involved in improving the health of Adamawa communities. They have been a key ally of the government, gaining recognition for our support in the development of the Primary Health Care (PHC) system from the community to the policy level. In 2014, efforts in health met the needs of over 700,000 people residing in areas of operation comprising of five counties and 63 health facilities in Michika and Noman. These were largely supported by two projects the Integrated Service Delivery Programme (ISDP) under the MCHIP consortium led by JHPIEGO and the Regional Primary Healthcare (RPHC) and Mubi Nurses and Midwifery Training School (MNTS) Programme supported by Bread for the World (BFDW) respectively and their work in the past year has to addressed basic health needs of the majority of the population by supporting high impact interventions. We supported the vaccination of 20,000 children and ensured the treatment of 65,000 others from life-threatening illnesses. Close monitoring of mothers during pregnancy ensures safe health for the mother and child. More than 13,825 women were provided with ante-natal services that included preventive treatment for malaria. In addition, curative services were offered to more than 144,000 people in health facilities supported by Red Cross that included the Mubi Hospital, the main referral hospital supporting Mubi and Noman, and where 450 major surgeries including caesarean sections were performed during the year. Supporting the training of nurses and midwives to address the severe shortage of qualified health workers in the underserved rural areas in South Sudan has been a cornerstone activity for the health programme (Interviewed IDPs Camp official on 27th January, 2019). In 2014, we supported the training of 26 Certified Clinical Nurses and Midwives who graduated from the Mubi Nurses Training

School in Mubi State and were deployed to various health facilities throughout the country. In addition, supporting the recruitment of 45 health staff in various cadres greatly improved service delivery, especially for mothers and children. The success of their work in 2014 was bolstered through working with community leadership to rally communities as partners in health services provision. INGOs worked with a variety of grassroots level entities that included Village Health Committees (VHCs), local authorities, Home Health Promoters (HHPs) and Health Committees. Working closely with the community on initiatives such as renovation of health and sanitation facilities and health education campaigns ensured their successful implementation. International Non-governmental Organization (INGOs) therefore, have provided a sense of belonging to people whose lives and livelihoods have been shattered by conflict is essential in helping them move beyond survival to recovery. Apart from responding with emergency aid, the project constructed or upgraded several schools and health facilities. This included water and sanitation facilities to enhance service delivery in the affected communities.

Conclusion

International Non-governmental Organization (INGOs) has played a significant role in Humanitarian assistance in Adamawa State are: emergence food aids, materials relief assistance and services, relief coordination protection and support services, basic nutrition, disaster prevention preparedness, reconstruction relief and rehabilitation, basic health care, ending violence against women and girls, agricultural development, basic drinking water, and basic sanitation and other sectors. INGOs such as Oxfam international and Red Cross participated in the Humanitarian assistance in Adamawa State. Their programme focused on assistance for returnees, legal aid service, water and sanitation, education, livelihood assistance and health. Some of the strategies adopted in achieving their objectives include; to ensure that, the right to health calls for evidence-based prevention, treatment and care services. Measures taken include; evidence-based prevention (family care health worker training, schools children immunization and disease prevention and life education and treatment, brief interventions, counselling, outreach work, psychosocial and pharmacological interventions in line with established sound medical practice. Engage Ministry of Education or appropriate agencies to improve capacity for more enrolment in school and assist in development of educational and vocational training programmes.

Recommendations

The study therefore recommends that:

- (i) International Non-Governmental Organization should continue with the role of humanitarian assistance for sustainable livelihood of the People in Adamawa State.
- (ii) International Non-Governmental Organization should make it as a matter of necessity to prepare a strategy for future assistance based on the actual local conditions as well as a need for field coordination and information dissemination in order to mitigate further crisis in the country.
- (iii) International Non-Governmental Organization should carry out further research to understanding the complicated social, cultural, and political background of the country after the civil war.
- (iv) International Non-Governmental Organization should involve the local communities in the provision of social intervention programme that will have direct impact on their lives.
- (v) International Non-Governmental Organization should focus more on providing economic empowerment to the people.

Authors' declaration

We declare that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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